

Synthesis of some New 1-*H*-(4,6-Dimethylpyrimidinyl)-3-arylamino-3-arylo-5-methylpyrazoles as Possible Potential Antineoplastics

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Syntheses of some new arylazopyrimidinylpyrazoles are reported. The arylazopyrimidinylpyrazoles have been synthesised by the reaction of 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones and 2-arylhydrazono-1-(2-chlorophenyl)aminobutane-1,3-diones with 4,6-dimethyl-2-hydrazinopyrimidine in good yields. Their structures have been established on the basis of elemental analyses and ir and pmr spectral data.

THE chemistry of pyrimidines and pyrazoles has been very extensively studied because many drugs include these rings. Many derivatives of pyrimidine have been used as therapeutic agents¹. 5-Phenylazo derivatives of pyrimidines have been found to have remarkable biological activities². Similarly a number of pyrazole derivatives have shown various biological activities³. For example, common sulphur drug Orisul has prolonged bacteriostatic action *in vivo*⁴. Furthermore, an arylazo grouping is of importance in promoting antineoplastic activity. In view of the important biological activities displayed by pyrazoles, pyrimidines and azo group, it was considered worthwhile to prepare compounds having both the moieties linked by an azo group.

The arylazopyrimidinopyrazoles (1) have been synthesised by the method developed in this laboratory by reacting 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones and 2-arylhydrazono-1-(2-chlorophenyl)aminobutane-1,3-diones separately with

4,6-dimethyl-2-hydrazinopyrimidine. The structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data. The reactivity of 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones and their chloro derivatives was smooth and the products were obtained in good yields.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Specord Carl-Zeiss recording spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. All the melting points are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel-G plates.

1-*H*-(4,6-Dimethylpyrimidinyl)-3-arylamino-3-arylo-5-methylpyrazole: 4,6-Dimethyl-2-hydrazinopyrimidine⁵ and 2-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione⁶ (starting materials) were prepared by the method reported in literature^{5,6}.

An alcoholic solution of 4,6-dimethyl-2-hydrazinopyrimidine (50 ml; 13.8 g, 0.01 mol) was added to a solution of 2-phenylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (2.81 g, 0.01 mol) in acetic acid (50 ml) and refluxed for 7 h. On cooling, the resulting shining crystals were recrystallised from DMF-water mixture, m.p. 100°. Similarly, other arylazopyrimidinopyrazoles were prepared by reacting suitably substituted 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-diones and 2-arylhydrazono-1-(2-chlorophenyl)aminobutane-1,3-diones (Table 1).

Important pmr, ir and electronic spectral data for some typical compounds are compiled in Table 2. In electronic spectra, only two bands were observed whereas in the case of nitro derivatives 6 and 7 (Table 2) an additional band at 270 and 278 nm respectively was observed. Similar

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-H-(4,6-DIMETHYLPYRIMIDINYL)-3-ARYLAMINO-4-ARYLAZO-5-METHYLPYRAZOLES

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							N	C	H
1	H	H	100	60	Light orange	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇	25.35 (25.58)	68.70 (68.93)	5.90 (5.48)
2	2-OCH ₃	H	135	50	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₇ O	23.50 (23.72)	66.60 (66.62)	6.20 (6.00)
3	3-OCH ₃	H	87	50	Golden	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₇ O	23.40 (23.72)	66.62 (66.82)	6.20 (6.00)
4	4-OCH ₃	H	127	55	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₇ O	23.50 (23.72)	67.00 (66.82)	6.25 (6.00)
5	4-CH ₃	H	125	55	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₇	25.50 (25.32)	69.40 (69.52)	5.95 (5.79)
6	4-Cl-2-NO ₂	H	180	57	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₂ Cl	23.90 (24.03)	58.70 (58.92)	4.60 (4.42)
7	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	105	50	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₇ O	22.70 (22.95)	67.65 (67.44)	6.00 (5.85)
8	2-Cl	H	155	52	Pale yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₇ Cl	23.20 (23.50)	63.00 (63.31)	4.50 (4.79)
9	3-Cl	H	175	55	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₇ Cl	23.35 (23.50)	63.10 (63.31)	4.55 (4.79)
10	4-OH	H	170	50	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ O	23.25 (24.56)	66.40 (66.16)	5.10 (5.26)
11	2-COOH	H	235	55	Reddish orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂	22.65 (22.95)	64.40 (64.63)	4.60 (4.92)
12	4-NO ₂	H	213	60	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₂	26.00 (26.15)	63.50 (63.76)	4.60 (4.83)
13	H	2-Cl	135	62	Light orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₇ Cl	23.10 (23.50)	63.10 (63.31)	4.95 (4.79)
14	2-OCH ₃	2-Cl	157	52	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ OCl	21.00 (21.16)	62.00 (61.74)	4.70 (4.92)
15	4-OCH ₃	2-Cl	165	55	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ OCl	21.10 (21.16)	61.50 (61.74)	4.65 (4.92)
16	4-OC ₂ H ₅	2-Cl	140	50	Pale yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₇ OCl	21.05 (21.25)	59.60 (59.87)	4.70 (4.92)
17	2-Cl	2-Cl	145	53	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ Cl ₂	21.40 (21.68)	58.30 (58.53)	4.45 (4.21)
18	3-Cl	2-Cl	135	55	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ Cl ₂	21.35 (21.68)	58.35 (58.53)	4.45 (4.21)
19	4-Cl	2-Cl	173	55	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ Cl ₂	21.46 (21.68)	58.35 (58.53)	4.40 (4.21)
20	2-COOH	2-Cl	190	57	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂ Cl	21.00 (21.25)	59.60 (59.87)	4.10 (4.34)
21	4-OH	2-Cl	245	50	Orange	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₇ OCl	22.25 (22.63)	60.75 (60.97)	4.40 (4.62)

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT PMR, IR AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR SOME TYPICAL COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm
1	1 590, 3 350, 1 650, 860	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.5(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 7.0-8.2(m, 10-ArH), 8.2(H, s, NHC ₆ H ₅)	250, 415
2	1 595, 3 370, 1 645, 860	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.6(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 4.2(3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.5-8.0 (m, 10-ArH), 8.0(H, s, NHC ₆ H ₅)	252, 418
3	1 595, 3 365, 1 650, 865	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.5(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 4.0(3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.5-8.0 (m, 10-ArH), 8.1(H, s, NHC ₆ H ₅)	255, 415
4	1 590, 3 365, 1 650, 860	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.5(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 4.2(3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.2-8.0 (m, 10-ArH), 8.2(H, s, NHC ₆ H ₅)	240, 420
5	1 590, 3 360, 1 650, 860	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.5(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 4.0(3H, s, CH ₃), 7.2-8.0(m, 10-ArH)	255, 415
6	1 585, 3 360, 1 655, 865	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.5(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 7.0-8.2(m, 9-ArH), 8.4(H, s, NHC ₆ H ₅)	250, 270, 415
7	1 590, 3 360, 1 650, 865	2.0(3H, s, pyrazole 5-OH ₂), 3.6(2 × 3H, s, pyrimidine-4,6-OH ₂), 7.8-8.2(m, 10-ArH), 8.4(H, s, NHC ₆ H ₅)	250, 278, 418

types of spectra for other aromatic azo compounds are reported in literature⁷. The presence of signal for NH around δ 8.0 was established by recording the pmr spectra after deuterium exchange. In deuterated compound 2 signal for NH at δ 8.0 disappeared, indicating that the signal at δ 8.0 is due to NH proton.

Antibacterial activity : All the compounds were screened *in vitro* against *Bacillus pumilus*, *Pseudomonas mongiferae*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Styphlococcus aureus* and *Styphlococcus pyrogenus*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by the cup-plate technique using the concentration range 0.5–1.0 mg mol⁻¹. Compounds 2 and 9 were active against all the organisms. Compounds 3, 4, 8, 12 were active against *B. pumilus* and *V. cholerae*. Rest of the compounds were inactive against all the organisms.

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References

1. E. A. FALCO, L. G. GOODWIN, G. H. HITCHINGS, I. R. ROLLO and P. B. RUSSELL, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1951, **6**, 185; A. GOLDBERG, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1951, **18**, 895; K. L. WIERZCHOWSK, E. LITONSKAO and D. SURGER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 4621; J. P. HOWARD, N. ØRVIK and M. L. MURPHY, *Cancer Chemother.*, 1966, **50**, 287.
2. J. HAMSPHIRE, P. HEBBOM, A. M. TRIGGLE, D. J. TRIGGLE and S. FICKERS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 745.
3. H. G. GARG and C. PRAKASH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 175; W. C. J. ROSS and G. P. WARWEEK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1364; E. HARRMAN and J. GABLIKO, *Cancer Chemother. Rep.*, 1961, **14**, 85; S. RICH and J. G. HORSFALL, *Phytopathol.*, 1952, **42**, 457; M. GNARNERI, *Bull. Chim. Farm.*, 1960, **99**, 259.
4. G. W. RAIZISS, L. W. CLEMENCE and M. FREIFELDER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 2789; M. P. V. BOARLAND, J. F. W. MCOMIE and R. N. FIMMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4692.
5. G. M. KOSOLAPOFF and C. H. ROY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1895.
6. H. G. GARG and P. P. SINGH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 1104; *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1969, 1141; R. JAIN and P. PANDEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in the press.
7. G. HALLAR, *J. Soc. Dyers Colour*, 1979, **95**, 285; G. HALLAR, R. MARSDAN, J. D. HEPWORTH and D. MASON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1986, 123; 1984, 49; E. SAWICKI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 915.